

Business Intelligence (Computational Intelligence in Vehicle and Transportation System)

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ABSTRACT

The Traffic and Transportation system is big problem in the world. So business intelligence in vehicle and transportation system solve this problem and solution with the help of new technologies. In the computational intelligence in vehicle and transportation system used computer electrical & electronic conversion technology management.

KEYWORDS: Computational intelligence, vehicle & transportation system, next generation vehicle & transport traffic control management, public transfer system, sensors, vehicle

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I. INTRODUCTION

The computational intelligence in vehicle & transportation system is associate rout to solve. This case under traffic problem. The computational intelligence are different types of models of transportation- air, sea, road, rail & intersects quality of transportation of each mode. The vehicle & transportation system use vehicle, structure, conversion & operating system in the vehicle & transportation system created technology based on geographically, cultural, social science and environment. The transportation system uses a traffic control management system.

This intelligence system tracks the vehicle illegal driving skill active specific search location in that field of computer version & social department. Due to suddenly improvement the vehicle intelligent system. The computational intelligence system is Need to control traffic-related accidents. In fact, the automate tracking of vehicle is needed to Monitor. The roads & expressway, they are many traffic parameters that should be calculation as over high-speed, yellow-line off-road driving performed the road.

Figure 1: An overview of vehicle to transportation scenario

The vehicle & Transport system based on share information in the from of vehicle to transportation, vehicle-to-to vehicle, vehicle-to-road side zone in this case are three main process are:- traffic efficiency, road safety, power efficiency used in this system.

1.1. In-vehicle sensors:-

The computational intelligence in vehicle & transportation system identifying the different of sensors to create application that continue to address following are:-[1] traffic control and parking difficulties [2] longer time communication [3]maximum level of oxygen emission [4]increase the number of road accident another is of implement a vehicle presenting as well enhancing the driving experience figure1 detection some many widely use sensors in vehicle today life.

Fig:-1 Different types of in-vehicle sensors:-

1.2. Environment category:-

Figure2:- environment monitoring system [a] road weather condition, [b]surface state [c] pollution system.

In this system in vehicle & transportation system environment category information is selected from sensors developed in permanent to different roads condition through the calculation of road temperature, road, condition, number of chemical &function group (figure 2)

1.3. traffic management category:-

Figure3:-traffic system [a]lane calculation system[b] surveillance [c]parking system[d]automatic toll system [e] special transportation [f]interaction control.

This system are implement the traffic control direction inroad and area [figure3] this system are two different way [1] fixed surveillance system of fixed platform use camera and sensors it are create on the highway on the consumer .the second system called as surveillance on the highway uses sensors and cameras enable in vehicle and transportation support system.

1.4. the new technology system:-

[Figure:-case Study scenario]

In this computational intelligence in vehicle & transportation system performance a case study sensor technologies can be combine the information and conversion technologies to implement the transport the system and implement help- support [1]the car is increase in the accident due to create suddenly and the vehicle take stuck internal [figure3]

II. Literature Review:-

In this Literature Review study a detailed GIS database of vehicle and transportation network accident location, hospital, ambulance location, police and fire zone was prepared was spatial analysis such as connection. In this system a real-time knowledge-based system fir decision support in the association of integrated traffic control planning to the occurrence of non-requirement congestion. in this in vehicle and transportation use of traffic connection system travel time decrease between 1.9% and 2.9% and typical stop speed reduced between 14.8% and 55.9%.

The computational intelligence in vehicle & transportation system GPS in traffic control. In their study application of GPS was improvement in collection traffic data such as travel time speed and delay on 64 path roads in the state of Maharashtra. This system are two multiple -agent knowledge based system developed to present decision support for real-time management .this present system was evaluated and general application of multiple -agent architecture for intelligent in vehicle and transportation system.

The intelligence in vehicle and transportation system, social-economic system environment take a input system and highway, road traffic management efficiency and urban transport system indication as the output system. this system study show that in vehicle and transportation implement the overall efficiency of transportation.

The present in vehicle and transportation system based on emergency response management for India city present the uses information regarding the different division and operation route during the suddenly emergency system. In this computation intelligence system in vehicle and transportation system based on the land used, building

active as per control the building .efficiency and effectives of the best services was the studied and based on this an suddenly response control system and improvement.

III. Research methodology:-

The proposed in vehicle and transportation system an improvement number of vehicle and transport economic conditional create a new interest in implement of new real-time motion-picture process. Itnote from the previous study that there are more commercial system proposed but they have different condition, shadows, dust, storms & light transformation also there are illegal driving activity such as yellow line drive able to detection therefore this research paper study a many features are computational intelligence in vehicle & transportation system learning algorithm to real time motion sequence. the author of this paper video-based computational intelligence in vehicle & transportation system.

In the many vehicle features are track instead of location just entry vehicle to made that fixed for different environment occlusion and lighting conditions. This system different between cars & truck features track. The in vehicle system tracking system is implement on four main stage. To in vehicle and transportation system implement the first step is to suggest of the view into single vehicle and tracking each vehicle internal a tracking area. A simple external motion frame. After detect the suggest the vehicle from external view, the ahead step is compute traffic parameters such as vehicle speed in different line of the expressway road.

The research study is extract the video frames from other side of expressway every time driving .in this a previous four many layer convolution neural internet model was used to transportation feature for prediction of driver’s illegal active during expressway driving.

After that of new combine feature maps is connection into one pattern, which will be the input of our process model to final classification of the traffic violation systems. The computational intelligence in vehicle and transportation road-traffic monitoring dataset was utilized in this dataset the simple motion video are select according the different environmental condition to made the system runs best combine to state-of-the-art system.

This system Research methodology steps are explained in the upcoming subsection of this paper

IV. Conclusion:-

In This system, we conferred the understanding related to location of vehicle illegal activity develop by the automate traffic management system. In system improvement to predict the driver's illegal active during expressway driving. the main object of this system to the consider the latest learning technical system to calculate traffic illegal parameters without focusing in many study in this system combine of transformation features and multiple architecture of algorithm effective combine for best classification result. so in this computational intelligence system using V-ITS, python, computer version open tool used utilize. in a future study in this system many traffic violation is addition record the different types of vehicle.

V. Future Enchancement:-

In our future work, we consider other means of Intelligent transportation & vehicle system infrastructure with

communication connection in an effort to reduce congestion & travel time. This system to limit the release of carbon emissions into the atmosphere, cut back on fuel consumption & implement road safety.

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